

Application of blockchain in BIM: a systematic review

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Abstract. Looking around, we see a change in all aspects of the digital industry, education, or the economy. The digital sector has witnessed a larger volume of transformation. Significant work and changes and improvements have been made in the field of design and manufacturing industry. The digital sector, as well as the construction sector, are witnessing digital transfers. Technology is evolving in solving various problems arising from all industries. The Blockchain is also moving towards the construction industry. Combining blockchain with BIM (building information modeling) is a great combination. Blockchain is really useful in the manufacturing industry. The blockchain is a chain of linked blocks in which each block relates to the block before it. The main characteristic of blockchain is to ensure information security. All the information is held in the blockchain in a codified and hashed form that has been encrypted. The blockchain is used for the accuracy of information transacted between two actors. The overall structure of blocks in the blockchain consists of two main parts. The first one includes the main information of the block in hashed form and the second part includes the address of the prior block in hashed form. In different construction projects, these data can include the smart contracts concluded between the employer, contractor, and consultant and also the correspondences done with different organizations, evaluation of workers' work hours. The structural information is the most significant data in the sensitive projects the accuracy of which should be assessed, since filtering such information leads to heavy casualties. The research method is descriptive with the Goal of getting acquainted with blockchain and combining it with the construction industry and building information modeling.

Keywords: blockchain, projects, BIM, construction, technology

1-Introduction

A blockchain is a digital, decentralized public document of data, assets, and all related transactions that is executed and shared among network participants. Although most associated with digital cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin, blockchain is seen as an emerging technology that can transform the current digital operating landscape and business practices of finance, computing, government services, and almost any existing industry. Transform. The main hypothesis behind blockchain is the creation of a digitally distributed agreement that ensures that data is decentralized across multiple nodes with the same information and that no user has full network authority. This provides transparency and increased data security. While initially designed only for financial transactions with the aim of creating a system that enables secure data transfer between the two parties without the need for intermediaries, later with the exponential development of various cryptocurrencies in recent years, the extremely destructive capacity of blockchain is evident became. Emphasizing trust and collaboration between participants, the blockchain reorganizes existing workflow paths in each organization in which it is implemented, and includes many benefits, including shared learning, instant data exchange, and automated contract execution, Network security and improved collaboration.

Figure 1: General concept of BCT blockchain technology (Chris Linton 2017)

Figure 1 shows that there are 5 steps in blockchain, which include: 1- Transaction 2- Block 3- Confirmation 4- Hash 5- performance. On the other hand, from the beginning to the end of the blockchain transaction can be seen in Figure 1.

Building Information Modeling

building information modeling has found wide applications from design and construction to operation and even demolition of buildings. This technology helps the project manager and stakeholders to make the right decision at each stage by digitally displaying the building specifications. Building information modeling All construction management activities according to the contract documents are related to two categories of drawings and specifications, so that with the help of drawings, the quantity of work and its quality are determined based on technical specifications. In general, BIM adds 3D modeling components to specific drawings and related specifications. This feature is that each member of the design shown in BIM, in addition to its three-dimensional physical nature, provides a set of information about the various activities and tasks of construction management. This information relates to the entire project life cycle, from feasibility studies to conceptual design, first and second phase studies, preparation, construction and installation, commissioning, operation period and even its completion. So if we want to summarize BIM in a short sentence, the process of producing and managing building information will be throughout its life cycle. In other words, the BIM model is a three-dimensional digital representation of the physical and functional characteristics of a building.

At present, the use of technology and the complete digitalization of the construction industry are still in the early stages. However, with the advent of technologies such as BIM + intelligent digital technology, all participants, and the entire management of the building design and construction process, can work together in a common platform. In the construction industry, the level of production, trade and management can also be effectively integrated, project data and management information are interconnected, and the era of designing and building sustainable buildings under BIM + smart digital technology will come.

Literature Review

According to (Nawari, Ravindran,2019) Research and Table 1, we find that 61 blockchain keywords are listed in articles, books, websites, Thesis.

Table 1. A summary of the literature on blockchain and related topics (Nawari, Ravindran,2019).

Methodology

This research is written using past and futuristic information to manage and examine the integration of building information modeling and blockchain. The research is based on the current blockchain review. In this research, literature review, definitions, development, current blockchain information and beam are presented. We deal with the main parts of the blockchain, which include smart contracts and so on.

Blockchain Technology

Block is a combination of the two words Block meaning block or piece and Chain meaning chain. Literally, blockchain means blockchain. A block is a space that can store a certain amount of information. By joining these blocks together, a

chain of blocks is obtained that contains interconnected data. This connection is made with hashes. Hash is the same cryptographic code that is based on the information in a block. Hashs are a set of numbers and letters that contain the entire information of a block. When a block is written and its information is completed, a hash is assigned to it, and this hash will be placed in the next block to determine if the new block is a continuation of the previous block. Also, the production of these hashes continues and the previous block hash is placed in the next block, and by following the hashes, the first generated block can be reached. For example, this hash is the first bitcoin block known as the Genesis Block. Anything can be turned into a hash and encrypted. With the hashing algorithm, large data can be reduced to a few letters and numbers, and in this way, the information of a block can be converted into a multi-bit expression.

In the figure number 2 you can see the components of a blockchain, which includes the genesis block, hash, previous block hash, etc ...

Figure 2. The structure of a blockchain (author)

The digital infrastructure of the blockchain network can be divided into two layers of code:

- **Fabric layer:** A blockchain's data structure is expressed as a linked list of blocks in which transactions are ordered. The data structure of the blockchain consists of two fundamental elements: pointers and a linked

list. A linked list is a list of chained blocks with data and pointers to the previous block. Pointers are variables that refer to the position of another variable, and a linked list is a list of chained blocks with data and pointers to the previous block. The Merkle tree is a binary tree of hashes. Each block contains the root hash of the Merkle tree and information like the preceding block's hash, timestamp, nonce, block version number and current difficulty goal. For blockchain systems, a Merkle tree provides security, integrity and irrefutability. The blockchain system is built on Merkle trees, cryptography and consensus algorithms. Because it is the first in the chain, the genesis block, i.e., the first block, does not contain the pointer. To protect the security and integrity of the data contained in blockchain, transactions are digitally signed. A private key is used to sign transactions, and anyone with the public key may verify the signer. The digital signature detects information manipulation. Because the data that is encrypted is also signed, digital signatures ensure unity. As a result, any manipulation will render the signature invalid. The data cannot be discovered because it is encrypted. It cannot be tampered with again, even if it is caught. The sender's or owner's identity is also protected by a digital signature. As a result, a signature is legally linked to its owner and cannot be disregarded.

- **Application layer:** Smart contracts, chaincode and decentralized applications (DApps) make up the application layer. The application layer protocols are further subdivided into the application and the execution layers. The application layer comprises the programs that end-users utilize to communicate with the blockchain network. Scripts, application programming interfaces (APIs), user interfaces and frameworks are all part of it. The blockchain network serves as the back-end technology for these applications, and they communicate with it via APIs. Smart contracts, underlying rules and chaincode are all part of the execution layer. Although a transaction moves from the application layer to the execution layer, it is validated and executed at the semantic layer. Applications give instructions to the execution layer, which executes transactions and ensures the blockchain's deterministic nature.

Privacy in Blockchain

One of the main advantages of blockchain is its security. Blocks are always stored in chronological order, and it is very difficult to change a block after it has been

added to the end of the blockchain. Each block has its own hash code, as well as the hash block that precedes it. If a hacker wants to edit a block, the hash of that block will change.

This means that the hacker will have to change the hash of the next block in the chain, and this process will continue. Therefore, to change a block, a hacker must change every other block after it, which requires a lot of computational power to do so. Although blockchain uses consensus algorithms, it is still vulnerable to a 51% attack. In these cases, the attacker controls more than 50% of the total blockchain computing power and gains the ability to overcome other participants in the network. However, this type of attack is unlikely to occur, because its implementation requires a lot of effort and computing power.

Smart contracts

With the advent of blockchain technology and the creation of the world's first digital currency (Bitcoin), the method of sending and receiving money, documents and documents has changed and intermediaries such as banks are gradually being phased out. The alternative to this system is SMART CONTRACT technology. Simply put, smart contracts take on the task of trading. A process that is already performed by a third party. Like all contracts in our daily lives, like written contracts or software contracts, a smart contract has the same terms as a contract; However, unlike traditional contracts, the terms of the smart contract run as zero and 1 or code running on a blockchain network such as Atrium. This is usually done by intermediaries for trading jobs. In fact, a smart contract is a program that can be stored on the blockchain and activated under certain pre-determined conditions. These contracts are used to automatically execute the agreement, so all contract participants can reach a final result very quickly, without interference and in a fraction of the time. These contracts also activate the workflow automatically, and when the conditions are right, the next activity begins. (Bhargavan, et al. 2016, Dhawan, 2016)

Smart contracts are written in a variety of programming languages (including Solidity, Web Assembly, and Mickelson). In the Atrium network, each smart contract code is stored on the blockchain, allowing anyone interested to check the contract code and current status to confirm its performance. Figure 3 shows the differences between smart contracts and traditional contracts.

Figure 3. The difference between smart contracts and traditional contracts (author)

• Advantages of Smart Contract

Because smart contracts are based on Blockchain technology, they have high security and speed, are cost-effective, and at the same time offer a great variety to users.

- Security: The smart contract is intelligently distributed among all nodes in the network. This eliminates the possibility of losing or changing it illegally.
- Low cost and high speed: These contracts are executed automatically and eliminate the need for intermediaries and third parties.
- Variety: There is a wide variety of smart contracts that you can choose from and change some of the clauses according to your needs.

• Disadvantages of smart contract

But smart contracts, just like any other technology, are not without flaws and have disadvantages.

- The human factor: Codes are written by humans in smart contracts, and humans can make mistakes! If the smart contract is on the block, it can no longer be changed. One of the most famous human errors about smart contracts happened to The DAO. The developers' mistake in writing this code cost user dearly, and some hackers were able to exploit the mistake and steal about \$ 60 million.
- Uncertain legal status: No country has yet enacted rules for smart contracts. As a result, it is possible that some countries will soon adopt a series of

regulations in this area, which will change the legal status of this type of contract.

- **Cost of writing:** Smart contracts cannot be implemented without programming. It is necessary to use one or more expert programmers to write this type of contract, and of course the internal structure of the contracting companies must be compatible with Blockchain technology.

Applications of blockchain technology

Blockchain technology should be introduced as one of the greatest innovations of the 21st century due to its high upward impact in various industries and sectors. One can easily understand the impact of this technology on human life these days in one sentence, also Governments, businesses and other organizations are trying to explore and even implement blockchain technology in various fields, and many of these fields have nothing to do with digital currencies. Blockchain can bring security, immutability, traceability, and transparency across a distributed network. Thus, Blockchain, relying on these unique features, is a viable option for implementation in areas where traditional infrastructure is inefficient.

AEC

The full form of AEC is “Architectural Engineering and Construction.” The acronym describes the collaboration of architects, engineers, and construction professionals on residential, commercial, or industrial construction projects to ensure their smooth completion. These three disciplines are integral to the project from design to execution.

- **Architecture:** Architects design the concept for the construction, restoration, or refurbishment of buildings.
- **Engineering:** Engineers oversee the construction and maintenance projects necessary in the realization of that concept.
- **Construction:** Construction project managers and their skilled laborers execute the design.

Challenges AEC industry

The biggest challenge facing the AEC industry is workforce shortages. Between an aging workforce and a large skills gap, it can be very hard to find the talent the industry needs. Architecture, Engineering, and Construction positions

require highly skilled leaders with safety awareness, technical expertise, and project management skills, a combination that can be hard to find.

“The ability to find talent for the AEC industry is changing. Younger people are entering the workforce, older workers are leaving the workforce, and more people are working remotely,” explains Stacia Norman, Director of Construction Recruitment at Orion Talent, “We have a shortage of experienced people to fill the needs of the AEC industry. It will be a challenge to recruit, hire and retain talent in 2022; but, it can be done with the right recruiting team in place.

Future for AEC

This has been a turbulent time for the AEC industry due to the loss of revenue during the pandemic. Companies looking to evolve need to think outside the box and adopt new technology. They should start by identifying new segments and even locations to target, and then move forward by embracing the time and cost savings that can be achieved by moving to the Cloud or leveraging tech like BIM Level 2.

Blockchain and Project Management

In the information compression process, the focus of information management is due to technology. The blockchain can provide a reliable infrastructure for managing information during the construction cycle. Even if used in a building information modeling (BIM) project, the role of the blockchain is essential to managing information about who did what and when. We conclude that the blockchain offers solutions to many of the problems in building information management.

Blockchain and BIM

This section addresses issues related to the potential capabilities of BCT in scaling and enriching the BIM process. It explores various aspects of existing BIM workflow that could benefit from the integration of blockchain technologies. BIM is at the forefront of digital transformation in the AEC industry, encouraging collaboration and trust and simplifying data exchange. McGraw-Hill reports that BIM adoption increased to 71% in 2012 from 49% in 2009 [8,43]. BIM models

present a comprehensive design model of the building that can include all aspects of the structure, like architecture, structural elements, and MEP design areas. Further, several built-in plug-ins in BIM platforms, like Autodesk Revit, enable the simulation of external site conditions, geography, weather, as well as carry out energy analysis, building energy modeling, structural analysis, etc. In the future, BIM development will eventually aim to unify all design and analysis tools in one platform.

In terms of the benefits incurred from the adoption of BIM in the AEC industry, Cannistrato. studied data from 408 projects over 6 years, totaling \$558,858,574, to quantify how much BIM contributed to saving money. The report indicated that BIM saved more money and the project team became more collaborative in the process. Another example is the study by [66], which indicated similar results. Their investigation covered a set of 35 case studies between 2008–2010, which all indicate cost savings due to BIM usage. The study has also noted reduced times in project schedules, improved communication, greater information exchange, and higher levels of coordination. The data clearly implies that initial costs, such as hardware upgrades, software implementation, and training of personnel, are offset on the long term upon BIM implementation. However, the BIM process still bears a number of shortcomings. These include some limitations in the schema, technical toolset, and managerial aspects of the current BIM process. More specifically, these deficiencies involve:

an insufficient toolset or methods that can efficiently comment or mark upon Requests For Information (RFIs), no archive of BIM model changes and modification history, impracticality in the generated list of design errors, inapplicability of the integrated model for co-designing in real-time , a clear generation of comparative deviation reports contrast design changes between different file versions, detailed open model templates, insufficient communication standards and BIM model sharing that can lead to interoperability issues between different BIM tools, a lack of tools to map complex collaborative workflows and insufficient levels of interoperability, difficulties in assigning responsibilities and liabilities due to the overlap of roles and responsibilities, ensuring intellectual property protection, risk allocation, privacy, and third-party reliance and software agents, insufficient cyber-resilience of the software platform and consequent risks and liability to data theft, tampering, and other cyber-attacks, time-consuming re-modeling, conversions, and other repetitive tasks that could be automated during the

project phases , the lack of a legal framework detailing model data ownership and legal/contractual issues.

Conclusions

This article provides a comprehensive overview of blockchain and its applications in the construction industry and BIM. The construction industry seeks sustainable development that faces the challenges of energy consumption and economics in the construction industry. The development of smart technologies has many benefits for the construction industry. However, the main function of blockchain and bim in designing a building and sustainable construction process is focused on the use of smart energy and construction management. The future of blockchain technology is somewhat bright because of the way governments and businesses seek to stimulate innovation and applications. It is quite clear that one day a general blockchain will be created that anyone can use. Blockchain fans expect the technology to be embedded in task-specific automation to help in all areas. The evolution of blockchain technology in recent years has increased the demand for blockchain specialists. Companies also plan to use blockchain programs in their areas of business to reap the benefits.

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